

Atrial Tachycardia or Long RP Supraventricular Tachycardia!

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Description

The above electrocardiogram (ECG) was obtained in a patient with intermittent palpitations. The rhythm reveals regular narrow-QRS complex tachycardia at 133 beats per minute (BPM) as indicated by the green arrows in the rhythm strip. The atrial rhythm consists of negative P waves in the inferior leads, II, III and aVF, fusing with the T waves (red arrows) suggestive of a non-sinus origin. The initial impression, also suggested by the EKG machine automated reading, was atrial tachycardia.

Closer scrutiny, however, of the P waves reveals that they are absent (blue stars) before the 8th and 14th QRS complexes. The absence of P waves despite the persistence of the QRS complexes makes atrial tachycardia highly unlikely, in which case a dropped atrial beat would be expected to result in a dropped QRS complex as well. Therefore, a more plausible explanation is that the rhythm is actually junctional or supraventricular tachycardia (SVT) with retrogradely conducted P waves and a long RP interval, with intermittent lack of VA conduction causing the dropped atrial beats.

Discussion

SVT is often symptomatic, resulting in hospital admission. It is most commonly caused by atrioventricular (AV) nodal reentry (AVNRT), orthodromic AV reentry (AVRT) or atrial tachycardia [1]. Typical AVNRT involves antegrade conduction down a slow pathway with retrograde conduction along a fast pathway, causing a pathognomonic short RP SVT. Long RP SVT can be due to antegrade conduction down a fast pathway and retrograde conduction up a slow pathway [2]. AVRT in the form of permanent junctional reciprocating tachycardia (PJRT), and atrial tachycardia also cause long RP SVT, which makes it difficult to differentiate these arrhythmias from atypical AVNRT [3].

The RP to PR ratio of greater than 2 has been suggested to favor atrial tachycardia over other forms of long RP tachycardias [4]. SVT with fewer P waves than QRS complexes rules out atrial tachycardia or orthodromic AVRT as these arrhythmias depend on atrial activation [5]. The mechanism, therefore, is more likely atypical AVNRT with intermittent VA block, as shown in the example above.

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References

1. Kotadia ID, Williams SE, O'Neill M. Supraventricular tachycardia: An overview of diagnosis and management. Clin Med (Lond). 2020 Jan;20(1):43-47.
 2. Harvey M. Spotting the difference: short versus long RP tachycardia explained.
 3. Jiménez-Díaz J, González-Marín MA, González-Ferrer JJ, Higuera-Sobrinó F. Long RP interval tachycardia. What is the mechanism? J Arrhythm. 2017 Jun;33(3):242-244.
 4. Yagishita A, Hachiya H, Higuchi K, Nakamura T, Sugiyama K, Tanaka Y, Sasano T, Kawabata M, Isobe M, Hirao K. Differentiation of atrial tachycardia from other long RP tachycardias by electrocardiographic characteristics. J Arrhythm. 2014 Oct;30(5):376-381.
 5. Lau YR, Kay GN. Supraventricular Tachycardia With Something Missing. Circulation. 2018 May 8;137(19):2076-2079.
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